
Postgraduate Student Accommodation and Outreach Centre Malaysia Contract Analysis

Submitted by: Miguel Ângelo Camelo Ferrão Moreira

Student ID: H00231775

Submitted to: Dr. Adekunle Oyegoke

MSc. Construction Project Management

Contracts and Procurement

D31PZ

DECEMBER 2015

HERIOT WATT UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF ENERGY, GEOSCIENCE, INFRASTRUCTURES & SOCIETY
CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SUSTAINABLE BUILDING DESIGN

Assumptions

This report assumes that the mode of procurement is Design and Build because it is easy to find local companies that know the local building regulations. The works must be completed in 18 months and before the start of the class session 2017/2018. Heriot Watt is going to send some equipment's from UK that need to be storage on site. The political and economy situation of Malaysia is very stable.

List of Tables

Contents

List of Figures	Error! Bookmark not defined.
List of Tables	iii
1 – Introduction	1
2 – The General Principle of Law Governing Construction Contracts	2
3 – NEC3 ECC Standard form of Contract and Composition for the Project.....	3
4 – Conditions of Contract Guiding Payment in the NEC3 ECC.....	5
5 – Conditions Governing Contractual Programme	6
6 – Disputes Resolution Methods in NEC3	8
7 – Comparison of NEC and FIDIC	10
8 – Conclusion	12
9 – References	13

1 – Introduction

Nowadays projects in the construction industry are becoming more complex involving many types of contractors, sub-contractors and suppliers. A need to establishing a legal relationship between the participants involved is important. The contract is the right way to do it by evidenced in writing all the agreements, obligations, duties and risk allocation between the participants (UKESSAYS).

A standard form of contract is more suitable due to several advantages like a fair and balanced allocation of the risk, the repetitive use makes it easier to understand its strength and weakness, the use of this form of contract in disputes allows judges to follow previous decisions on precedent contracts. Another important factor for the standardisation of contract is that they provide a legal framework which recognize rights and obligations of the parties involved as well as the power and duties of the contract administrator (UKESSAYS).

The aim of this report is to design a contract using the standard form NEC3 ECC and advice the Principal of the Heriot Watt University on a post contract for the construction of a £1 million Postgraduate Student Accommodation and Outreach Centre in the Malaysia Campus.

2 – The General Principle of Law Governing Construction Contracts

The South Africa Council for the Quantity Surveyor Profession (2014: 15) defines a contract as "... an agreement with the serious intention to be legally bound". The contract is the most important stage of a business relation, it establish the mutual promises by defining the rights and obligations of the parties involved on the contract. Contracts are private law celebrated by the agreement between parties with high flexibility in the arrangement of terms and conditions. There are some limitations in the conditions imposed by legislation and common law. After signed the contract is valid and states the arrangements and how they should be manage (COUNCIL, 2014, OYEGOKE, 2015).

For the existence of a valid contract occur there are some requirements that need to be satisfied. First of all the parties should be competent to contract, they should arrive to a consensus and agree on it, the subject matter of the contract must be legal and not be contrary to public policy so formalities required by law should be observed. Finally, contracts should be voluntarily celebrated for some reasonable matter and seriously managed in order to avoid conflicts and disputes (COUNCIL, 2014, OYEGOKE, 2015).

The foundation of a contract is the agreement between parties and this has consequences in the management of time, cost and disputes settlement. If the agreement on the contract is not clear the tools for solving this issues will not be clear (OYEGOKE, 2015). The agreement is put on the test with the "offer and acceptance" for example, during a tender an offer is putted in place with a proposal contract but no contract is formed until the client accept the offer. Many counteroffers may be discussed but just one can be accepted when consensus is reached becoming the law that governs the contract (COUNCIL, 2014, OYEGOKE, 2015).

3 – NEC3 ECC Standard form of Contract and Composition for the Project

The NEC is a simple and direct standard form of contract. It was developed to promote collaboration between parties instead of focus in the liabilities and obligations (GOULD, 2007, OYEGOKE, 2015).

The main principles of NEC are flexibility, simplicity and clarity, and the incentive to good management. Nine main clauses were defined and applied to all NEC standard contracts. To customise NEC3 contract six main options were added to the core clauses. These six main clauses define payment method and the allocation of the risk, and are related to the format of procurement that was establish. Secondary options are added for further customisation. One from two options W1 and W2 is chosen to provide disputes resolutions mechanisms. Seventeen secondary options can be added as necessary to meet the employer's requirements and to allocate specific risks between both parties. Two of these secondary options Y are related to the Housing Grants, Construction and Regeneration Act 1996, and Contracts (Rights of Third Parties) Act 1999 and are used in the UK only. A series of additional conditions known as Z Clauses can be added to provide both parties to insert bespoke terms or amendments to the contract. However, these clauses should be avoided because as they are not standard clauses the impact of these clauses can in terms of disputes resolutions bring more harm than benefit as no precedent is known and judges cannot follow previous decisions (GOULD, 2007, OYEGOKE, 2015).

To compose the NEC3 ECC contract for this project and taking in consideration all the assumptions the nine core clauses as usually were adopted. A Lump Sum priced contract with activity schedule (option A) was selected to help the contractor to have cash flow during the whole programme and provide all conditions for an early completion if possible. This option allows to reduce administration since payments are made by activity completion there is no need to track all information of the work done on the activity. High certainty on the price and less risk for the client is achieved since the design is allocated to the contractor. This option is more suitable for this project than others because Option B and D need to use bill of quantities and since the design is made by the contractor he can have some limitation ability on doing them. These options add administration and surveyor responsibilities to the

client. Option E and F are not suitable for this project due to the high values involved. These options allocate all the cost risk to the client. Option C give reasonable cost certainty but is not suitable for design and build (GOULD, 2007, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Since the project is based outside the UK W1 option was adopted as a procedure for disputes resolution method. This procedure will be explained further in this report. For the same reason neither of the location-specific secondary options y(UK)2 and y(UK)3 were selected because they do not apply outside UK (NEC³, 2005).

From the secondary options eight clauses (X3, X4, X5, X7, X13, X14, X16 and X20) were chosen. Multiple currencies (X3) is needed because the contract price is in pounds and the contractor is going to be payed in the local currency. Parent Company Guarantee (X4) the values in the contract are high so this guarantee is needed in case of insolvency of the contractor. Sectional Completion (X5) is required to allow Heriot Watt to use part of the Outreach Centre to store equipment's arriving from the UK. Delay Damages (X7) are adopted because the project must be finish before lecture year 2017/2018 if not contractor must pay the consequential losses from inability HW from using the facilities. A Performance Bond (X13) is needed to guarantee fit for purpose since the design is contractor responsibility. To help the contractor to start and accelerate the project an advance payment is going to be provide and an Advance Payment (X14) clause will give protection on the money invested. Since measures were taking to provide the contractor with enough cash flow to complete the project on time Retention (X16) is putted in place to guarantee project quality. Key Performance indicators (X20) are adopted to provide benchmarking performance for other projects (GOULD, 2007, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Price Adjustment for Inflation (X1) and Changes in the Law (X2) are not used because the short period of the contract and the economic and political stability of Malaysia. Bonus for Early Completion (X6) is not needed because HW does not need the facilities before the agreed date. Partnering (X12) is not needed since the contract is just for this project and HW does not have outer projects in the near future. The contract is responsible for the design and no Contractor's Liability Limitation (X15) should be provided. Low Performance Damages (X17) and

Limitation of Liability (X18) are not need because the maximum penalty will be applied as stated in the previous clauses (GOULD, 2007, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Finally Z Clauses are added, copyright of the design and prohibited materials. In this terms de contractor design but give the rights of the design to HW as well as the right for the specification of some materials (NEC², 2013).

Example: NEC contract was used by the Olympic Delivery Authority in the Olympic Games 2012 in London.

4 – Conditions of Contract Guiding Payment in the NEC3 ECC

The conditions guiding payments in NEC3 are stated in the core clause 5, the main option clause will complete the mechanism of payment, Option A is to be adopted in this contract.

In this option the price for work done to date (PWDD) is the sum of all the activities completed in the activity schedule (Clause 11.2.27). The final price “contract sum” is the summation of all the activities in Lump Sum prices (Clause 11.2.30). The activity schedule is only a payment document used to determine the payments and should be related the operation programme (Clause 31.4). However, the activity schedule is not work or site information (Clause 54.1). A work programme should be provided by the contractor and in case of not presenting it, one quarter of the (PWDD) is retained until the programme and all information is submitted (Clause 50.3). Changes in the activity schedules can be made if the contractor submit them to the PM (Clause 54.2). These changes can be rejected if they do not comply with the Clause 54.3 (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Assessing the Amount Due (Clause 50) the amount due defines the assessment date for each payment. The first assessment is decided by the PM after negotiations with both parties and follow dates are schedules (Clause 20.1). The amount due is calculated following the clauses 50.2. A deduction of the Retention agreed in clause

X16.1 must be made. Half of the retention is paid on take-over and the other half in the final assessment (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Payment (Clause 51) the PM certifies a payment within one week of each assessment date (Clause 51.1) and each certified payment is made within three weeks (Clause 51.2) otherwise interest should be paid. If the amount due is corrected by the PM for any mistake or compensation event, or by following a decision of a tribunal or adjudicator interest in the correcting amount is paid (Clause 51.3) (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Clause 52 Define Cost is used to access the value of compensation events. Main option clause A Defines Cost in the Clause 11.2(22) and they determines additional payments to the contractor. Variations can occur in the contract by changes instructed by the PM or for events that are not responsibility of the contractor. This variations generate compensation events and they are addressed in the clause 6 (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Example: At the end of which activity (option A) the contractor will submit the PWDD to the PM. PM certify the payment after one week, the contractor receives the payment after three weeks with the deductions of the retention.

5 – Conditions Governing Contractual Programme

The conditions guiding the contractual programme in NEC3 are stated in the core clause 3 Time. The contractor is responsible for submit the contract programme to the PM (Clause 31.1) with all information related to the work programme, important dates as stated in Clause 31.2. If the contractor does not provide the programme PM can deduct 25% of all payments as stated previous in the report (Clause 50.3) (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

The PM can only define two dates, the starting date and the completion date (Clause 30). The contractor cannot start work on site until the first access date (Clause 30.1) and the PM must certifies completion within one week of completion (Clause 30.2). The contractor does the work in accordance to the programme so that all key dates

are achieved (Clause 30.3). Key dates are different from sectional completion dates. They state only dates which work is to meet specific conditions stated in the contract data. In this contract a sectional completion option (X5) was selected to store equipment's that will arrive from the UK before completion of the work. This information is stated in the contractual programme as well as the date where the contractor is liable to pay delay damages (X7) (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

After the submission of the programme the PM has two weeks to make a statement whether accepts or give reasons to for rejection. The reasons for not accepting the programme are stated in clause 31.3. When a revised programme is submitted to PM data recording the actual progress of the work and its affect upon the timing of the remaining work need to provide as well as the impact on the completion date and possible compensation events (Clause 32.1). The accepted programme can be reviewed if the contractor chooses, the PM instructed, a compensation event affects the programme or if regular intervals are defined in the contract data (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

The Employer must allow access to the site on or before the access data (Clause 33.1) otherwise the contractor can claim more time and a compensation event occur (Clause 60.1.2). The same principle occurs if the PM instruct the contractor to stop or not to start a work (Clause 34.1). According to clause 60.1.4 contractor can claim (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

The Employer will take over the work no later than two weeks after completion date and if the contractor finish the works earlier than the completion date the employer is not bond to take over the works (Clause 35.1). Partial possession is possible if the employer starts to use any part of the works and for this reason he takes over the works (Clause 35.2) unless it is for a reason stated in the work information or to suits the contractor method of works. The PM certifies the dates (Clause 35.3) (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

The PM can request a quotation to accelerate the completion date (Clause 36.1), the contractor submits the quotation or gives reasons no to do within the period of replay (Clause 36.2) (NEC¹, 2013, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Example: The contractor must submit a programme with all the activities and key dates. The programme should translate the activities to do in a time frame. A key date is for instance a date where the PM should supply a material to the contractor or finish a work in the critical path that stops the contractor of carrying out the rest of the works.

6 – Disputes Resolution Methods in NEC3

The NEC standard form of contract was created to promote collaboration and teamwork between the parties involved. This contract have clauses that are flexible, simple and clear to avoid disputes (GOULD, 2007).

In the core clauses there are some clauses that promote discussion and avoid disputes. Clauses 16 Early Warning are a very important part of NEC contracts. They consists in identifying potential problems before they occur. They are not considered as claims however, if ignored money or time can be expended by both parties. Early warnings can be given by both parties PM or Contractor by notifying the other as soon as either became aware of any matter which could increase the total price, delay completion or meeting a key date or impair the performance of the works in use (Clause 16.1). There are consequences if the contractor does not give an early warning when he should had (Clauses 61.5 & 63.5). Both PM or Contractor have the right to instruct the other to attend a risk reduction meeting (Clause 16.2) in other to co-operate in managing part of it (Clause 16.3) (GOULD, 2007, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Under the clause 17 both PM or Contractor have to notify the other in case of any ambiguity or inconsistency is found (Clause 17.1). If any compensation event occur due to this clause the assessed compensation is under clause 63.8 (NEC³, 2005).

All this clauses help to avoid disputes and claims. In other to resolve disputes main option clauses W are putted in place. Since this project is to be delivery outside the UK option W1 was adopted (NEC³, 2005).

The principal dispute resolution in NEC3 is adjudication. By contract the parties appoint an Adjudicator that acts impartially to solve the disputes (Clauses W1.1 & W1.2). The disputes are notified and referred to the adjudicator in accordance to the adjudication table which identify the reason of dispute, the party claiming and the time scales (Clause W1.3). A dispute is not referred to the tribunal unless it has first been referred to the adjudicator (Clause W1.4.1) (GOULD, 2007, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

This method of dispute resolution allows both parties to at any time to refer a dispute to the adjudicator and solve them in minimal time and without all the consequences of solving it in tribunal. In case of the adjudicator cannot solve the dispute the tribunal is the last option. The adjudicator cannot be witness in tribunal (Clause W1.4.6). This method of dispute resolution unfortunately does not always comply with the law of the place where the contract is delivered and a third option W may be necessary to compose for particular international jurisdictions (GOULD, 2007, NEC³, 2005, OYEGOKE, 2015).

Example: Contractor or Employer can claim for time or money but sometimes just one is conceded. For example in case of bed whether the contractor can lose money because he has to stop the work but still have to pay the employees but just can claim for time as the action was not created by the Employer. In case of the employer miss a key date for instance supply a specific material the contractor can claim for time and money.

7 – Comparison of NEC and FIDIC

NEC and FIDIC are both standard forms of contracts and in both a person acts in behalf of the employer. Engineer in the FIDIC and PM in the NEC making the last one more collaborative and focus in good project management (GERRARD, 2014).

Regarding the payments both contracts can be payed using bills of quantities or in stage payments (FIDIC clause 12.2) but, NEC goes further with the main options enabling payments to be cost reimbursable or target cost. In NEC the assessing and payment is stated in core clause 5 and completed with the mechanism of payment chosen from the main clause. FIDIC clause 12 deals with measurements and evaluation and clause 14 contract price and payments. This clauses are highly prescriptive of all the procedures and time schedules making the process slower and time consuming. NEC provides a shorter timescale within three weeks of assessment day (clause 51.29) while in FIDIC the whole process takes 56 days (clause 14.7.b) forcing the contractor to make provisions to accommodate financial costs and passing them to the client. However, an advanced payment (clause 14.2) must be done to the contract to provide cash flow for the works while in NEC a secondary option X14 advanced payments is compulsory. Both contracts enable cost variations claims in FIDIC and compensation events in NEC but they deal with it differently. FIDIC splits the components in time and cost and deals with them separated in different stages. NEC manages them together gaining ability to better accommodate changes in budget and time (BESAISO, 2012, FIDIC, 2010, GERRARD, 2014, NEC³, 2005).

Concerning the programme in both contracts the employer states the starting date, a completion date, access date and any sectional date with some differences in the terminology. In FIDIC the contractor have to submit a time programme to the engineer and to update it when becomes outdated (clause 8.3). This programme is just to explaining how the contractor intend to carry out the works and is not part of the contract data while in NEC is a more detailed set of documents that become the tool by which the change is assessed, progress is monitored and assists the management of early warnings and compensations events. The programme is so important for NEC that deduction from payments are putted in place if the contractor failure to submit it. In both contract the contractor should inform of any event or

circumstances that may affect time or cost (FIDIC clause 8.3) but in FIDIC the contractor is only obliged to claim for more money or time after the event occur. The NEC has a more collaborative approach using early warnings from both parties to identify such possible events and use risk reduction meetings to manage those events. In FIDIC an extension of time is granted to the contract if a delay occur by any of the clauses in clause 8.4 or delays cause by local authorities (clause 8.5). Both contracts allow for delay damages (FIDIC 8.7), X7 in NEC. In NEC the PM can required a quotation for acceleration of the work and include a bonus for early completion (BESAISO, 2012, FIDIC, 2010, GERRARD, 2014, NEC³, 2005).

In terms of disputes resolution both contracts recognise that variations are the traditional cause of disputes and they try to avoid them in early stages. FIDIC try to avoid disputes by limitation them to 10% after which new process should be agree while in NEC is more flexible and does not have any limits of variations but requires quotations to fix the price before the variations starts. If any disputes arise both contracts have similar mechanisms for resolution. FIDIC adopted the Dispute Adjudication Board (DAB) under clause 20 while NEC under main option W appointed the Adjudicator. Both mechanisms are similar they preselect a neutral expert to make decisions but these experts cannot enforce the decisions made just referee. The DAB have advantages to the NEC adjudicator since the members visit the site frequently and are aware of the progress of the works making it possible to take wise decisions. In another hand, NEC is quicker making decisions in 28 days compared to the 84 days of FIDIC. The mechanisms in NEC seeks for changes in contractual relationship to prevent disputes and try to avoid them upstream when they may arise while DAB in FIDIC improves the way to resolve and settle them downstream (BESAISO, 2012, FIDIC, 2010, GERRARD, 2014, NEC³, 2005).

8 – Conclusion

The construction industry is a complex business that involve large amounts of capital, and this capital need to be protected. The contract is a good way to allocate the risk and the obligations of each part involved. It is crucial that a standard for of contract is selected as these are better known in the industry and easy to apply.

In this report two standard forms were study and we can see that both can be applied. FIDIC is a more prescriptive contract with clauses that protect both parties in different aspects while NEC tries to promote collaboration between parties on trusting environment.

9 – References

- BESAISO, H. 2012. *Comparing the Suitability of FIDIC and NEC Conditions of Contract in Palestine*. M.Sc. Management of Projects, University of Manchester.
- COUNCIL, T. S. A. 2014. *Understand the Basic Principles of Construction Law in the Built Environment*, South Africa, The South Africa Council for the Quantity Surveying Profession
- FIDIC 2010. *Conditions of Contracts for Construction*, FIDIC.
- GERRARD, R. 2014. *A Comparison of NEC and FIDIC*, NEC.
- GOULD, N. 2007. *NEC3: The Construction Contract of the Future*, Singapore, Fenwick Elliott.
- NEC¹ 2013. *Course Notes*, NEC.
- NEC² 2013. *Additional Public Sector Z Clauses Required to Comply With the Requirements of The Public Contracts Regulations 2015*, NEC.
- NEC³ 2005. *Engineering and Construction Contract*, NEC.
- OYEGOKE, A. 2015. *Lecture Notes Contracts*, Edinburg, Heriot Watt University.
- UKESSAYS. *The Importance of Using Standard Forms of Contracts in Construction Industry* [Online]. UK Essays. Available: <http://www.ukessays.com/essays/construction/the-importance-of-using-standard-forms-of-contracts-in-construction-industry.php> [Accessed 09/11/2015].